

My journey through a green path[†]

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The practice of green chemistry in chemical synthesis has received wide attention because of the general awareness of ill effects of chemical pollution in the environment. A chemical reaction is primarily guided by its design, use of solvent, catalyst and energy. The organic solvents are more or less toxic and thus use of alternate green solvents such as water, ionic liquids and supercritical fluids is appreciated. Catalysts play an important role in chemical synthesis. In the context of Green Chemistry catalysis has received intense interest both in academia and industry. Thus, development of both homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysts with high efficiency (TON) has become a major goal. However, the heterogeneous supported catalysts are of much current interest because of their primary advantages such as, ease of separation, reusability, improved efficiency due to stable active site and better steric control of a reaction intermediate, compared to their homogeneous counterparts. These qualities made them very promising for applications in industry. Although use of thermal energy at the expense of electricity is common for a reaction the application of other devices which consume less electrical energy such as microwave, ultrasound, ball milling, visible light (sunlight/LED bulb) is getting momentum. We have developed several organic solvent free reactions, a number heterogeneous supported catalysts which showed improved efficiency, ball milling and visible light induced reactions. We have also reported C-H functionalization via C-H activation, which controls generation of waste.

Keywords: Green synthesis, green solvent, green catalyst, use of less energy, minimization of chemical waste.

Introduction

My journey started late eighties with a small group in a small lab in the Department of Organic Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science. The 'Green Chemistry' did not get its official stamp yet. However, several groups, particularly in USA were advocating on the philosophy of Green Chemistry towards practice of Chemistry. This wave moved me too and I started to practice my chemistry on this path.

Results and discussion

My group focussed on the design of toxic organic solvent free reactions primarily based on surface mediated solid phase reaction. The first breakthrough we made, is solvent-free Michael reaction on the surface of alumina (Scheme 1)¹. The process is very simple. The reactants are adsorbed on the surface of alumina and the reaction mixture was stirred for few minutes at room temperature. The majority of the

Scheme 1. Surface-mediated solid phase Michael reaction.

reactions were complete within 10 min. After the reaction was over, the reaction residue was washed with ethyl alcohol and the alcohol extract was evaporated to leave the product which was practically pure. This process has general applicability to a variety of substrates. Most significantly, this reaction was performed without using any toxic organic solvent in the entire process. The other advantages of the protocol are very fast reaction at room temperature, use of no conventional catalyst and cost effectivity with reusability of alumina. These features constitute the basic parameters of a green reaction.

[†]Acharya J. C. Ghosh Memorial Lecture (2017).

This paper has received wide attention by academia and industries in subsequent years. However, this journey was not at all smooth at the initial phase. I have been discouraged by a few of my own colleagues with the comments that this type of chemistry will go nowhere and will not get any recognition. I have faced insulting remarks from a few of my 'so called intelligent' fellow chemists when I presented this work in a seminar. However, I did not give up as I was certain that this will be the future path for Chemistry. Needless to mention, that today the philosophy of Green Chemistry is accepted by all the chemists in academia and industry worldwide. The subject 'Green Chemistry' has been included in the undergraduate and postgraduate curriculum in the syllabus prescribed by UGC in this country too.

This protocol of 'Solvent free surface mediated solid phase reaction has been efficiently applied for Mukaiyama Aldol reaction² (Scheme 2), Mukaiyama Michael reaction³ (Scheme 3), selective tetrahydropyranlation of alcohols (Scheme 4)⁴, regioselective acylation of aromatic ethers with carboxylic acids (Scheme 5)⁵ among others⁶⁻⁸.

Scheme 2. Mukaiyama Aldol reaction of silyl enol ethers with aldehyde.

Scheme 3. Mukaiyama Michael addition of silyl enol ethers to methyl vinyl ketone.

Scheme 4. Tetrahydropyranlation of alcohols.

Scheme 5. Regioselective acylation of aromatic ethers with carboxylic acids.

Another attractive way of solvent-free process is neat reaction under thermal condition in absence of any catalyst. A few representative examples from my group are: synthesis of dihydropyrimidinones (Scheme 6)⁹, synthesis of α -amino phosphonate by a one-pot three-component conden-

Scheme 6. Green approach towards synthesis of dihydropyrimidinones.

sation of carbonyl compound, amine and diethyl phosphite (Scheme 7)¹⁰ and acylation of alcohols, amines and thiols (Scheme 8)¹¹. In these reactions the reactants are mixed together in neat and the mixture was heated at a certain temperature (monitored by TLC). When the reaction was over the product was isolated by distillation, if it is liquid or by crystallization for solid compounds.

Scheme 7. Synthesis of α -aminophosphonate by a one-pot three-component condensation.

Scheme 8. Highly efficient acylation of alcohols, amines and thiols under solvent-free and catalyst-free conditions.

The next phase of journey starts with reaction using ionic liquid as catalyst and reaction media. Ionic liquid, is usually composed of an organic cation and an inorganic anion and hence it bears cationic as well as anionic character. Those which are liquids at/below 100°C are, in general called ionic liquids. Ionic liquids are non-volatile, thermally stable and apparently less toxic. Thus these compounds have received attention as an alternative to toxic organic solvents.

We observed a dramatic influence of a task specific ionic liquid [bmIm]OH in Michael addition of active methylene compounds to conjugated ketones, carboxylic esters and nitriles (Scheme 9)¹². Interestingly, the reaction with α,β -unsaturated ketones produced the mono-addition product whereas, α,β -unsaturated nitriles and carboxylic esters led

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Scheme 9. Michael addition of active methylene compounds to conjugated ketones, carboxylic esters and nitriles.

to bis-addition products. This report demonstrates a unique example of the influence of an ionic liquid towards controlling the course of the reaction. This paper has received wide appreciation as evident by more than 500 citations. Other significant reports in this area constitute regioselective conversion of epoxide to vicinal-halohydrins using [AcMIm]X (Scheme 10)¹³, synthesis of thioethers, thioesters and dithianes (Scheme 11)¹⁴, synthesis of highly substituted pyridines (Scheme 12)¹⁵, stereoselective debromination of vicinal-dibromides (Scheme 13)¹⁶ and synthesis of 2-aryl benzimidazoles (Scheme 14)¹⁷.

Scheme 10. Regioselective conversion of epoxides to vicinal-halohydrins.

Scheme 11. Ionic liquid as catalyst and reaction medium for the synthesis of thioethers, thioesters and dithianes.

Scheme 12. Three-component synthesis of highly substituted pyridines using ionic liquid.

Scheme 13. Stereoselective debromination of vicinal-dibromides by [pmim]BF₄ under microwave irradiation.

Scheme 14. Synthesis of 2-aryl benzimidazoles promoted by ionic liquid, [pmim]BF₄.

We changed our focus to the application of benign metal nanoparticles as catalyst. As the surface area of nanoparticles are large they are more efficient as catalyst compared to parent metal. In addition, because of the lower redox potential it is easier for a metal nanoparticle to transfer electrons than the parent counterpart. These characteristics make the metal nanoparticles more effective.

We are interested to explore less expensive and benign metal nanoparticles such as copper, iron, cobalt etc. for catalysis. Under this program we demonstrated chemoselective reduction of aromatic nitro compounds by copper nanoparticles/ammonium formate (Scheme 15)¹⁸, copper nanoparticles catalyzed synthesis of S-aryl- and S-vinyl dithio-

Scheme 15. Highly chemoselective reduction of nitro compounds by copper nanoparticles.

carbamates in water (Scheme 16)¹⁹, sustainable phenyl-selenylation of aryl iodides and vinyl bromides using copper

Scheme 16. Copper nanoparticle-catalyzed synthesis dithiocarbamates in water.

nanoparticles as catalyst in water (Scheme 17)²⁰, hydrogenation of azides over copper nanoparticles surface using ammonium formate in water (Scheme 18)²¹ and highly selective reduction of nitroarenes by iron(0) nanoparticles in water (Scheme 19)²².

Scheme 17. Phenyl-selenylation of aryl iodides and vinyl bromides using copper nanoparticles.

Scheme 18. Hydrogenation of azides over copper nanoparticle surface using ammonium formate in water.

R = EWG, EDG

Scheme 19. Highly selective reduction of nitroarenes by iron(0) nanoparticles in water.

It is well known that water is greenest reaction medium. However, water is also successful in inducing the reaction through H-bond formation. An important contribution from our

lab is transition metal free synthesis of S-aryl dithiocarbamates using aryl diazonium fluoroborate in water at room temperature (Scheme 20)²³.

R = EWG, EDG

Scheme 20. Transition metal-free synthesis of S-aryl dithiocarbamates in water at room temperature.

Our group is also actively engaged in the application of heterogeneous supported metal catalyst for useful reactions. We have developed a recyclable simple alumina supported copper catalyst which finds wide applications. A few significant contributions are: coupling of thiols with aryl halides (Scheme 21)²⁴, regioselective ring opening of aziridines and epoxides and subsequent cyclization to functionalized 1,4-benzoxazines and 1,4-benzodioxanes (Scheme 22)²⁵, solvent controlled halo-selective selenylation of aryl halides for the synthesis of unsymmetrical organomono- and bis-selenides (Scheme 23)²⁶ and solvent controlled selective N-arylation of cyclic amides and amines with bromo-iodoarenes (Scheme 24)²⁷.

Ar = aryl, heteroaryl
R = aryl, heteroaryl, alkyl etc
X = Br, I

Scheme 21. Copper catalyzed cross-coupling of thiols and aryl halides.

Scheme 22. Copper-catalyzed ring opening-cyclization using 2-iodophenols.

Scheme 23. Solvent selective selenylation of iodo- and bromobenzene.

a heteroatom containing unit. A representative example is cobalt catalyzed remote C-4 functionalization of 8-aminoquinoline amides with ethers via C-H activation under

Scheme 24. Solvent controlled differential N-arylations of cyclic amides and amines.

In another green initiative we investigated to replace the costly and toxic palladium and toxic ligands which are often used in various reactions as catalyst system, with cheap and apparently non-toxic metals like copper, nickel and cobalt without any ligand. The most significant contribution in this project is cross coupling of alkynyl bromide and alkyne catalyzed by a combination of nickel acetylacetonate and copper iodide to produce unsymmetrical diyne in absence of any ligand (Scheme 25)²⁸ among others²⁹⁻³⁰.

R_1 = aryl, heteroaryl
 R_2 = aryl, heteroaryl, alkyl

Scheme 25. Ni-Cu catalyzed synthesis of unsymmetrical conjugated diynes.

visible light irradiation providing an easy access to α -heteroarylated ether derivatives (Scheme 26)³¹ among others³²⁻³⁴.

Mechanochemistry where reactions are initiated by direct application of mechanical energy, produced in a ball milling apparatus, is an emerging branch of Green Chemistry. This powerful tool provides a solvent and often catalyst free process with less reaction time and using minimum energy³⁵. A couple of significant reports from my group are solvent, ligand and metal free synthesis of unsymmetrical diarylchalcogenides (Scheme 27)³⁶ and solvent free one pot synthesis of 1,2,3-triazole derivatives³⁷ under ball milling.

The visible light mediated photocatalyzed reaction is another important development towards green path. The reactions are performed at room temperature under this process and thus sensitive functionalities remain unaffected. A significant contribution from my group is visible light

Scheme 26. Visible-light-mediated cobalt-catalyzed alkylation of quinoline amide derivatives.

The C-H functionalization via C-H activation is an important development towards green synthesis. This strategy avoids prefunctionalization of a C-H bond towards coupling and hence it reduces the number of steps. The C-H bond is activated by a neighbouring directing group which is usually

Scheme 27. Synthesis of unsymmetrical functionalized aryl/alkyl/heteroaryl chalcogenides.

Scheme 28. Visible light photo-catalyzed direct one-pot synthesis of organoselenides from aryl- and heteroaryl amines.

photocatalyzed direct conversion of aryl/heteroaryl amines to selenides at room temperature (Scheme 28)³⁸.

Conclusion

Green Chemistry is a philosophy and this is a continuous process through constant development of newer tools. This article provides a brief account of my group's efforts in this direction. If this account provides encouragement and enthusiasm to any researcher, the field of Green synthesis will be enriched.

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